

Extraction of Palladium (II) with 2-Thenoyltrifluoroacetone : Cyclohexane-Water System

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The extraction behaviour of palladium(II) with 2-thenoyltrifluoroacetone (HTTA) in cyclohexane from aqueous perchloric acid media has been studied in detail. $\text{PdClO}_4(\text{TTA})\text{HTTA}$ exists at $\text{pH} \lesssim 2.0$, while at pH values $\gtrsim 2.0$, $\text{Pd}(\text{TTA})_2$ species is found to be extracted into the organic phase. The mechanism of extraction has been discussed. The logarithm of the distribution ratio of HTTA between cyclohexane and 0.01M HClO_4 is 0.52 ± 0.02 .

2-Thenoyltrifluoroacetone (HTTA) is a well known analytical reagent and considerable work on the solvent extraction of its complexes has been reported¹. HTTA has also been used for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of palladium using BuOH as solvent².

Studies using benzene for extraction have already been reported³, and in the present communication the mechanism of extraction reactions and the nature of the extracted species have been reported for the $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{HClO}_4/\text{Pd}^{2+}/\text{HTTA}/\text{cyclohexane}$ system.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched silica cells was used for the absorbance measurements.

A Leeds and Northrup pH indicator with a glass-calomel electrode assembly was used for the determination of pH.

Palladium perchlorate solution was prepared⁴ from palladium chloride (Johnson Matthey and Co.) and was standardised by estimating palladium gravimetrically as dimethylglyoximate. Solutions of appropriate concentrations were obtained by suitable dilution.

HTTA (E. Merck) was recrystallised and dissolved in cyclohexane to obtain a standard solution.

All other chemicals were of reagent grade.

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Distribution Ratio of HTTA : A 10 ml solution of HTTA of known concentration $[\text{HTTA}]_{\text{tot}}$ in the organic phase was mixed with equal volume of $0.01M \text{HClO}_4$. After equilibration, concentration of HTTA in the aqueous phase $[\text{HTTA}]_{\text{aq}}$ was determined by noting the absorbance at $268 m\mu$ and reading from the calibration curve. The HTTA concentration in the organic phase at equilibrium $[\text{HTTA}]_{\text{org}}$ was obtained by difference from $[\text{HTTA}]_{\text{tot}}$. The distribution ratio of HTTA is then

$$D_{\text{HTTA}} = ([\text{HTTA}]_{\text{tot}} - [\text{HTTA}]_{\text{aq}}) / [\text{HTTA}]_{\text{aq}}$$

The $\log D_{\text{HTTA}}$ value for cyclohexane was found to be $0.52 \pm .02$.

Calibration Curve for HTTA : HTTA was dissolved in NaHCO_3 buffer⁵ of $pH \sim 8.5$ (at $pH > 9.0$, HTTA decomposes into trifluoroacetic acid and acetylthiophene⁶). Measured volumes of this solution were diluted to 25 ml. maintaining $[\text{H}^+] = 0.01M \text{HClO}_4$ and the absorbances were noted at $268 m\mu$. Beer's law is valid.

Two solutions having the same palladium ($5.0 \times 10^{-5}M$) and perchlorate ion concentration but different acidity were mixed to give a desired level of pH . 10.0 ml. of this solution were equilibrated with an equal volume of HTTA solution in cyclohexane. After equilibration aliquots of the aqueous phase were withdrawn for the determination of palladium content.

Palladium was determined spectrophotometrically (at $505 m\mu$ and at a pH of 4.8) using *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline⁷. $\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}-\text{HNO}_3$ buffer was used for maintaining the

Fig. 1. The variation of distribution ratio of palladium(II) D_{Pd} with pH at different HTTA concentrations. $[\text{HTTA}] = \text{A} : 0.0005M; \text{B} : 0.001M; \text{C} : 0.0015M$ and $\text{D} : 0.0025M$.

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pH . The total palladium $[Pd]_{tot}$ and that in the aqueous phase $[Pd]_{aq}$ being known, palladium in the organic phase $[Pd]_{org}$ was determined by difference. All experiments were made in duplicate.

The distribution ratio of palladium is given by

$$D_{Pd} = ([Pd]_{tot} - [Pd]_{aq}) / [Pd]_{aq}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The distribution of palladium between cyclohexane, containing varying amounts of HTTA, and aqueous perchloric acid was studied at various pH values. The results are shown in Fig. 1, where $\log D_{Pd}$ is plotted as a function of pH for four different HTTA concentrations. In Fig. 2 $\log D_{Pd}$ is plotted against $\log[HTTA]$ at four different fixed pH values.

Fig. 2. The variation of distribution ratio of palladium(II) D_{Pd} with HTTA concentration at various pH values. $pH = A : 1.7$; $B : 1.9$; $C : 2.1$ and $D : 2.3$.

The plots in Fig. 1 show curves with variable gradients. As pH is increased, the slopes vary from unity to two, indicating the liberation of one hydrogen ion at pH values ≤ 2.0 and two hydrogen ions at pH values ≥ 2.0 . The slope of the curves of $\log D_{Pd}$ vs. $\log[HTTA]$ at fixed pH values in Fig. 2 is two, which indicates a 1 : 2 (Pd : TTA) species. Presumably, $Pd(TTA)_2$ species is extracted into cyclohexane at high pH values, since two hydrogens are liberated. At low pH values, only one hydrogen ion is liberated and the composition of the extracted species corresponds to $Pd(TTA)HTTA^+$. This charged species should not be extractable in cyclohexane and therefore it is reasonable to assume the association of a perchlorate ion to make the species neutral, i.e. $PdClO_4(TTA)HTTA$.

The extraction reaction, therefore, can be expressed as :

As *pH* is increased, more HTTA dissociates, and availability of TTA⁻ becomes greater, which replaces perchlorate ion and HTTA molecule associated with the extractable species and the composition becomes Pd(TTA)₂. The extraction reaction then becomes :

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